

A PUF-based Root-of-Trust for resource-constrained IoT devices

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Abstract—Ensuring cybersecurity resilience in far-edge IoT devices remains a significant challenge, as these systems often lack dedicated hardware security elements such as TPMs or secure enclaves. This paper introduces a cost-effective, SRAM PUF-based RoT architecture tailored for resource-constrained devices, enabling secure authentication and local attestation without relying on persistent key storage. Leveraging a commercially available SRAM module and a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor, the proposed framework enables robust and unforgeable key reconstruction, while a lightweight KDF binds the device identity to device-specific system properties (dynamic or static), thereby providing attestation capabilities in resource-constrained environments. A realistic telehealth monitoring scenario, involving an ECG device and a trusted gateway, demonstrates the feasibility of deploying the solution in real-world use cases. Extensive benchmarking results validate the low overhead of cryptographic operations and trustworthiness evidence extraction, highlighting the practicality of the proposed approach for scalable, resilient far-edge infrastructures. The presented solution contributes to the broader objective of reinforcing device-centric security foundations within the evolving landscape of critical IoT deployments.

Index Terms—Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs), Root of Trust (RoT), Internet of Things (IoT), Secure Authentication, Device Attestation, Cyber Resilience, Resource-Constrained Devices, Far-Edge Computing, Fuzzy Extractor, Key Derivation Function (KDF).

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern Internet of Things (IoT) infrastructures are increasingly pervasive, enabling seamless integration between the digital and physical worlds. As illustrated in Fig.1, these infrastructures span a variety of domains, including smart homes, transportation systems, community services, and national-scale

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applications, where smart devices such as sensors and actuators collect and exchange data through nearby gateway nodes. These gateways serve as intermediaries, allowing users such as homeowners or healthcare professionals to remotely access real-time information over existing network infrastructures [1]. This interconnectedness promotes automation, reduces human intervention, and improves both accuracy and efficiency, ultimately offering substantial socio-economic benefits.

Despite their functional advantages, the widespread deployment of smart devices in such heterogeneous and critical environments poses significant security challenges. These devices, especially those deployed at the far edge of the network, typically operate with limited computational and storage resources, and often lack dedicated secure elements such as Trusted Platform Modules (TPMs) or secure enclaves. Consequently, establishing a hardware-based Root-of-Trust (RoT) that is both reliable and cost-efficient remains a fundamental barrier to achieving robust security in resource-constrained edge environments.

In response to this challenge, Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs) have emerged as promising hardware primitives for enabling device-level security without the need for persistent key storage [2]. By exploiting uncontrollable manufacturing variations, PUFs generate device-specific responses to input challenges, offering a lightweight mechanism for identity provisioning and cryptographic key generation. While PUFs offer a compelling pathway toward lightweight hardware-based security, their integration into real-world systems must extend beyond mere device identity. In critical applications, it is not sufficient to authenticate the device per se, attesting the device’s operational trustworthiness is equally essential.

This work proposes an SRAM PUF-based authentication scheme accompanied by attestation enablers, tailored for resource-constrained far-edge devices. Our solution leverages an off-the-self SRAM module as entropy source, combined with a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor, offering robust key

Fig. 1. A generalized IoT architecture [1]

regeneration for cryptographic operations. A lightweight Key Derivation Function (KDF) further extends this capability by binding the derived PUF key to runtime system attributes, such as firmware integrity or dynamic stack metadata, allowing for context-aware trust evidence extraction. By embedding this approach into a realistic telehealth scenario, we demonstrate that device-centric trustworthiness monitoring can be achieved without reliance on specialized hardware, and within practical performance constraints.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Physically Unclonable Functions

Physically Unclonable Functions (PUFs), introduced in 2002 [2], are hardware security primitives that exploit intrinsic manufacturing variations to generate unique and reproducible device fingerprints, known as PUF tags. These tags are inherently unclonable due to complex, irreproducible fabrication processes, conceptually serving as physical analogues to one-way functions. They are particularly suited for on-demand cryptographic key generation, eliminating the need for persistent key storage (“no key-at-rest” property). Even with physical access, adversaries cannot replicate a device’s intrinsic properties, making PUFs ideal for device-centric identification and authentication. Furthermore, PUFs offer a cost-effective alternative to traditional methods where secret keys are server-generated and memory-stored [3].

PUFs exploit inherent hardware microstructures to generate unique, device-specific responses to input challenges, forming distinct challenge-response pairs (CRPs). As stated in [4], a module qualifies as a PUF if it satisfies:

- *Robustness*: Consistent responses to the same challenge across time and conditions.
- *Unpredictability*: No correlation between different responses from the same or different devices.
- *Unclonability*: CRPs are unique and infeasible to replicate, even by the manufacturer.

- *Physical Tamper-Resistance*: Any invasive modification attempts lead to device failure.

It is further assumed that the communication channel between the PUF and its host device is secure and cannot be intercepted or manipulated, as noted in [5].

Definition 1 (Robustness): A PUF instance PUF_A is robust if, under any two environmental conditions $cond_1, cond_2$ and for a given challenge $C \in \{0, 1\}^k$, it produces responses $R_1, R_2 \in \{0, 1\}^n$ such that:

$$\Pr [HD_{\text{intra}}(PUF_A(C, cond_1), PUF_A(C, cond_2)) \leq d_1] \geq 1 - \epsilon$$

where d_1 is the maximum allowable intra-device Hamming distance and ϵ a negligible error probability (e.g., 10^{-6}). Ideally, $HD_{\text{intra}} = 0\%$.

Definition 2 (Unpredictability and Unclonability): A PUF is unpredictable if, for any two challenges $C_1, C_2 \in \{0, 1\}^k$, the responses differ by at least d_2 :

$$\Pr [HD_{\text{intra}}(PUF_A(C_1), PUF_A(C_2)) > d_2] = 1 - \epsilon$$

It is unreplicable if two distinct instances PUF_A, PUF_B produce responses differing by at least d_3 for the same challenge C_1 :

$$\Pr [HD_{\text{inter}}(PUF_A(C_1), PUF_B(C_1)) > d_3] = 1 - \epsilon$$

Ideally, both HD_{intra} and HD_{inter} should be 50%. [6], [7].

B. Fuzzy Extractors

Despite advancements in enhancing the reliability of PUF circuits, noise remains a critical challenge. Zhang et al. [8] addressed dissipative filtering in discrete-time switched fuzzy systems with missing measurements, modeling data loss using a Bernoulli binary distribution. This probabilistic model characterizes the stochastic behavior of data loss during communication between the fuzzy plant and the filter.

To counteract PUF output instability, Gope et al. [9] recommended the use of *fuzzy extractors*, as originally proposed in [10]. Fuzzy extractors are widely used in PUF-based authentication to correct response errors caused by environmental variations, enhancing key stability and uniqueness. Secure sketches are typically constructed using linear codes, such as Hadamard, Hamming, repetition, Reed-Solomon, Reed-Muller, binary Golay, and BCH codes [11], [12]. Various error-correcting codes (ECCs) and decoding strategies have been proposed for fuzzy extractors in PUF-based key generation [13]– [17].

Two common constructions are the code-offset and syndrome-based approaches, both classified as linear schemes due to the linear relationship between the PUF response and ECC codewords. In the **syndrome-based approach** adopted here, the syndrome is calculated by multiplying a sequence w of n bits of the PUF response with the transposed parity-check-matrix H^T of the ECC (n, k, t) , so $h = wH^T$, and the syndrome is stored as helper data [18].

III. IMPLEMENTATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND REALIZATION OF AN SRAM PUF-BASED KEY DERIVATION FUNCTION

Building on the theoretical background of PUFs and their key properties of *robustness*, *unpredictability*, and *unclonability* described above, this section details the experimental implementation and characterization of the SRAM-based PUF considered here, along with key generation and reconstruction scheme followed. Also, a Key Derivation Function (KDF) that accompanies the proposed SRAM PUF construction is presented, which can be utilized for binding the physical identity of the host device (i.e. PUF-key) with any device-specific system property (static or dynamic), enabling the local attestation capabilities of the device.

A. SRAM-based PUF Instance Realization and Characterization

The first step in utilizing an SRAM module as a PUF is determining the available challenge-response pair (CRP) pool. Based on the number of CRPs, PUFs are classified as strong or weak. Weak PUFs digitize manufacturing variability into a limited number of stable, environment-robust responses, typically used for secret key generation. Strong PUFs support a large number of CRPs, making brute-force attacks infeasible even with temporary access; thus, they are preferred for authentication [19].

In SRAM PUFs, challenges may target the entire memory or specific addresses. Here, the latter approach is adopted, representing challenges as sequences of selected stable bits. Since the realized SRAM PUF operates in authentication mode, stable bit locations were identified using the data remanence method [20].

Prior to implementation, the following operational assumptions are defined: (i) only the manufacturer initially has physical access to the device; (ii) an adversary may access the helper data and challenges used in the PUF scheme; (iii) the security level targets a 256-bit key length; and (iv) the SRAM module must be commercially available and cost-effective. Based on these constraints, a systematic methodology was adopted to design and evaluate a reliable and secure SRAM-PUF instance:

- 1) **Embedded Platform Selection:** The initial design decision involved choosing an appropriate embedded platform to host the PUF system. Among the candidates considered, the Arduino Mega 2560 was selected due to its ease of debugging, widespread availability, low power consumption, and sufficient computational resources for far-edge IoT applications. It also offers extensive digital and analog I/O capabilities, which facilitates seamless integration with external memory modules via GPIO interfaces.
- 2) **SRAM Module Integration and Preliminary Evaluation:** The Cypress CY62256NLL-70PC was selected as the external SRAM module, serving as the entropy source. It is widely available, low-cost, and features 256 kbit capacity with automatic power-down functionality

to minimize power usage. This module was interfaced with the Arduino Mega 2560 to characterize its physical behavior. An initial evaluation was conducted by sampling all SRAM cells across five distinct chips, and the resulting binary strings exhibited a balanced distribution of '1's and '0's—indicating adequate randomness and suitability for a PUF-based construction.

- 3) **SRAM-PUF characteristics evaluation:** Following [20], stable and unstable memory bits of the SRAM were identified and from a total of 246,678 identified stable bits, a subset of 4,662 bits was used to construct a 2,331-bit response string to be used as a challenge, ensuring a sufficiently large challenge-response space. Since the most essential criteria for a PUF instance were fulfilled, the proposed device's robustness, unpredictability and unclonability characteristics were determined in terms of fractional HD.

To assess the operational characteristics of the SRAM-based PUF, a comprehensive experimental setup was employed, involving the generation of 10,000 challenges per SRAM chip by randomizing the positions of stable memory cells. Robustness was evaluated by selecting a single challenge (e.g., Challenge 1 on SRAM Chip 4) and repetitively applying it to the same SRAM module connected to an Arduino Mega 2560 board. The corresponding responses were recorded at 15-sec intervals over a continuous period of 96 hours. During this period, the SRAM module was periodically powered off and on to capture any variations induced by power cycling. This procedure was replicated across all evaluated SRAM chips. Fig.2 presents a indicative example of the fractional HD distribution obtained from one chip. As evident, from the corresponding histogram (red bins), the fractional HD distribution of the specific SRAM module is centered around 2.14%. This low deviation underscores the PUF's robustness, as the variation between repeated responses to the same challenge remained minimal over time. The remaining chips exhibited similar performance, with FHD values ranging between 2.08% and 2.2%.

Fig. 2. The SRAM-PUF crucial characteristics in terms of FHD.

Following the robustness assessment, the unpredictability

of the SRAM-PUF was evaluated. A single SRAM chip interfaced with an Arduino Mega 2560 was subjected to the previously generated set of 10,000 distinct challenges. The resulting responses were collected and analyzed in terms of fractional Hamming Distance (FHD). As shown in Fig. 2 (orange bins), the FHD distribution was centered at 47.9%, closely approximating the ideal 50%, thereby confirming the PUF’s high randomness and non-predictable behavior. The probability of obtaining identical outputs from two different challenges was negligible, indicating suitability for cryptographic applications.

To assess unclonability, the challenge set from one SRAM chip (e.g., SRAM No. 2) was applied across all other modules. Responses were captured and analyzed, yielding an FHD distribution centered around 48.26% (Fig. 2, blue bins), again closely matching the ideal value. Furthermore, robustness and unclonability distributions are well separated, without the presence of overlaps between them, highlighting that the creation of an identical clone of such a module is almost not feasible even by the manufacturer per se, whereas the false acceptance or rejection rate is equal to 0.

B. Key Generation and Reconstruction Scheme

As mentioned in the previous section, to eliminate the inevitable effect of noise in PUF’s responses, a fuzzy extractor should be utilized in order to create a practical key generation and reconstruction scheme. Here, a syndrome-based fuzzy extractor approach was followed. The proposed scheme is a modified version of [21] and it was successfully implemented very recently in [22] utilizing another type of silicon-based PUF class (arbiter-PUF) on a Xilinx ARTIX-7 FPGA, a device with by far greater computational capabilities than typical far-edge IoT devices. In the next subsection, the benchmarking of the proposed implementation will be presented, highlighting that the constructed scheme is also applicable when SRAM-PUFs and resource-constrained devices are considered.

C. The proposed KDF for enabling device attestation

Resource-constrained devices (IoT and far-edge nodes) often lack secure enclaves or TPMs, yet still require a hardware root-of-trust and PUFs have emerged as a lightweight alternative to stored keys. However, by itself a PUF only binds keys to the physical identity of the chip. The next step is to also bind keys to the device’s software state or configuration. This ensures that cryptographic keys are valid only when the device is in an expected, trustworthy state, enabling a form of lightweight attestation. Towards that direction, the KDF depicted in Fig.3 is proposed.

To generate the final key used for the device authentication, the proposed KDF, paired with the previously described SRAM-based PUF construction, requires two distinct inputs. The first is the PUF-derived key, generated according to the scheme detailed above, whereas the second is a runtime-specific property that reflects the current operational state of the host device. A straightforward example of such a property that can be utilized for the final key generation and

reconstruction is the hash of the authentic firmware image loaded during the device’s boot process. By combining this property with the PUF-based key, the KDF produces a final key that is valid only when the device is in a known and expected state. As the verifier holds the expected output of the KDF, any modification in the firmware will result in a different derived key, thereby causing the authentication to fail.

Fig. 3. The context of the proposed KDF for far-edge IoT devices

In place of a static property such as the firmware hash, a dynamic attribute, such as stack metadata can also be employed. Stack-related properties (e.g., memory address and size) provide insight into the device’s runtime execution behavior and are essential for enforcing control-flow integrity. When used as an input to the KDF, these dynamic values enable the detection of runtime anomalies and offer enhanced assurance of the device’s operational trustworthiness. Since control-flow integrity is a dynamic measurement, upon a request for a final key reconstruction, if such a system property deviates from the expected one, which is an indication of risk, the verifier will not authenticate the specific far-edge device. Essentially, by utilizing the KDF proposed here to generate an HMAC-key binding the PUF-based key with a system property, the establishment of a secret between the far-edge device and any verifier that intends to authenticate such a device can be realized.

IV. INSTANTIATING THE PROPOSED SRAM-BASED PUF CONSTRUCTION IN A REAL-WORLD RUNNING EXAMPLE

In order to demonstrate the applicability of the developed SRAM-based PUF implementation a realistic scenario was chosen from healthcare domain. This use case focuses on a typical telehealth and remote patient monitoring system, where an end-user device (e.g. Electrocardiography (ECG) device) transmits patient’s data to a gateway through a bluetooth interface and then the gateway to the backend of the service provider. Here, the main focal point is the interaction of ECG device, with is usually a low-end device with limited computational capabilities, with the gateway which acts here as a verifier. Two stages are considered in the authentication scheme, the enrollment and the authentication phase.

When the ECG device is initially introduced into the home network, it undergoes an enrollment phase, during which it is registered with a gateway. Following successful

enrollment, the device can be securely deployed within its intended application environment. During the authentication phase, the authenticity of the ECG device is verified by the gateway, and data is securely exchanged between those two devices. The proposed authentication scheme is designed to be adaptable across diverse scenarios and healthcare applications, supporting secure communication between heterogeneous devices, whereas it is agnostic to the underlying communication protocol employed between devices.

A. Experimental Setup

To evaluate the proposed SRAM PUF-based construction demonstrating also its applicability in a real-world use case, a realistic experimental test-bed for remote patient/telehealth monitoring was considered. A widely used in smart home applications, Raspberry Pi 3-based gateway was selected to act as a verifier in this specific scenario. As the connected medical device (CMD), an ECG device based on the Nordic nRF52840 System-on-Chip (SoC) was chosen, where the proposed SRAM PUF instance was instantiated.

B. Enrollment Phase

When a new low-end device (i.e. ECG), equipped with an SRAM-PUF module, needs to be added to the home network, it has to be registered to the gateway through the enrolment phase. During that phase, the ECG device transmits an enrollment request to the gateway along with its total number of the PUF challenges P_c (e.g. 100,000), which have been created by the manufacturer of the specific PUF instance and are stored within the internal memory of the device. Then the gateway, which in our working example serves as a trusted entity, randomly generates a challenge index $i \in \{1, P_c\}$, and transmits it back to the ECG device. Upon the challenge index reception, the ECG device calculates a fixed-size hash H_{FW} unique to the authentic firmware image loaded during the boot-up phase of the device, obtains the output of the PUF R_i by retrieving the challenge C_i for the ECG internal database and generates the corresponding syndrome $Synd_i$. The latter is stored locally as helper data, since it does not leak any vital information for the output of the PUF, but essential for future PUF-key reconstruction [23]. Then, the authentic firmware hash along with the PUF output are provided as inputs to the proposed KDF, resulting to the final HMAC-SHA-256 key K_i , which is transmitted and stored to the gateway along with the index i . This process is repeated for multiple challenge indices until the creation of a database $\{i, K_i\}$ in the gateway and a $\{i, Synd_i\}$ in the ECG.

C. Authentication Phase

After successful registration of the ECG device on the gateway, each time secure data exchange between those devices must be performed, the former should verify its identity and boot-state integrity. The authentication verification protocol described in this subsection leverages the proposed SRAM-PUF-based key regeneration mechanism and includes a

Algorithm 1: Enrollment Protocol for SRAM-PUF-Enabled ECG Device

Input: ECG device with P_c PUF challenges stored internally; Gateway (trusted)

Output: Gateway stores $\{i, K_i\}$; ECG stores $\{i, Synd_i\}$

1. ECG \rightarrow Gateway: Send registration request and total number of PUF challenges P_c ;
 2. Gateway:
 - Randomly select challenge index $i \in \{1, P_c\}$;
 - Transmit index i to ECG device;
 3. ECG device:
 - Retrieves challenge C_i ;
 - Computes firmware hash H_{FW} of authentic firmware image;
 - Evaluates $PUF(C_i)$ to obtain response R_i ;
 - Generates helper data $Synd_i$ from R_i using ECC and store it locally;
 - Derives final key $K_i = \text{HMAC-SHA-256}(R_i \parallel H_{FW})$ through KDF;
 - Transmit $\{i, K_i\}$ to the gateway;
 4. Gateway stores $\{i, K_i\}$ in its enrollment database;
 5. Repeat Steps 2–4 for multiple challenge indices to populate both databases;
-

gateway-issued nonce to ensure message freshness and prevent replay attacks.

To initiate authentication processes, the gateway randomly selects a challenge index i from its enrollment database and generates an one-time nonce N . The pair $\{i, N\}$ is transmitted to the ECG device and upon the challenge index and nonce reception, the device performs the following operations: (i) it computes the current firmware hash H'_{FW} based on the image loaded during its boot-up phase; (ii) it reconstructs the PUF response R'_i using i and the locally stored helper data $Synd_i$; (iii) it regenerates the final PUF-based key utilizing the proposed KDF, $K'_i = \text{HMAC-SHA-256}(R'_i \parallel H'_{FW})$; and (iv) it employs K'_i , that serves essentially as an attestation key, to sign the received nonce N , and a signature $T = \text{HMAC}(K'_i, N)$ is generated, which binds the reconstructed final key to the gateway-issued nonce. The device then transmits T to the gateway and validates the signature to confirm the authenticity and boot-state integrity of the device, since as a verifier it is aware of the nonce provided as well as the enrolled HMAC final key K_i .

The proposed authentication protocol offers several advantages particularly suited to resource-constrained far-edge IoT devices, namely:

- **Hardware-Tied Identity and Integrity:** The final authentication key is derived by binding the unique PUF response with the authentic firmware has, ensuring that both the device’s physical identity and its boot-state are validated during authentication.
- **Nonce-Based Freshness:** The gateway-issued nonce en-

sures that each authentication session is unique, protecting against replay attacks and enhancing session freshness.

- **Local Implicit Attestation:** The authentication process inherently verifies the device’s boot-up state. If the firmware hash or PUF reconstruction deviates, the authentication fails, providing implicit attestation without extra hardware.
- **Unforgeability and Resilience to Impersonation:** Since the regenerated key is tied to the device’s unique PUF and cannot be computed by another device, even with knowledge of the firmware and nonce, the protocol inherently resists device cloning.

Algorithm 2: Authentication Protocol for SRAM-PUF-Enabled ECG Device

Input: Gateway: Challenge index i , Nonce N ; ECG: $Synd_i$

Output: Gateway authenticates ECG device if $T = \text{HMAC}(K_i, N)$

1. Gateway:
 - Selects random challenge index i from enrollment database;
 - Generates an one-time nonce N ;
 - Transmits $\{i, N\}$ to ECG;
 2. ECG device:
 - Computes current firmware hash H'_{FW} from booted image;
 - Reconstructs PUF response R'_i using C_i and $Synd_i$;
 - Derives final key: $K'_i = \text{HMAC-SHA-256}(R'_i \parallel H'_{FW})$;
 - Computes signature: $T = \text{HMAC}(K'_i, N)$;
 - Sends T to the gateway;
 3. Gateway:
 - Retrieves enrolled key K_i ;
 - Computes $T' = \text{HMAC}(K_i, N)$;
 - **if** $(T = T')$ **then**
 - ⌊ Authenticated
 - **else**
 - ⌊ Malicious found
-

D. Performance Evaluation

Having comprehensively described the protocols utilized for the registration and authentication of a ECG device to a home network employing a trusted gateway, in this subsection an end-to-end performance evaluation of the proposed authentication mechanism is presented. This evaluation enables a thorough assessment of the computational overhead introduced by critical cryptographic operations, such as PUF-based key generation, firmware integrity verification, and nonce signing in each step of the aforementioned process and facilitates the identification of potential performance bottlenecks, particularly when deployed on resource constrained far-edge IoT devices such as ECG devices. This in-depth analysis provides valuable insights into the feasibility of secure communication

and PUF-assisted authentication, whereas highlights how local implicit attestation can be enabled in devices of that type.

A detailed breakdown of the benchmarking methodology is presented in Figure 4, which maps each operational phase to its corresponding performance metric and illustrates the interactions between components of the selected experimental setup. It should be noted that the benchmark results reported in Table I pertain to a particular deployment scenario in which both challenge and syndrome data are retrieved from an external SD card, since their size exceeds the capacity of the device’s internal storage memory. Also, in order to emulate a close to real-world scenario, the distance between the gateway and the ECG device was set at approximately 4 m. To evaluate the performance implications of the proposed mechanism, the time consumed by several key steps in the operational flow was measured, including data retrieval from storage, computation and preparation of the system for communication. This detailed breakdown facilitated a comprehensive assessment of whether low-end devices are capable of executing the specified tasks efficiently, without incurring significant latency or experiencing performance degradation beyond acceptable thresholds. An analysis of each benchmark performed as part of the evaluation process is summarized below:

- Benchmark 1:* This step captures the time required for device pairing over the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) interface, as well as for the exchange of authentication information (i.e. challenge index i and nonce N) between the gateway and the ECG. Given the distance-dependent nature of this metric, the average time measured was 2.374 sec.
- Benchmark 2:* During this step, the time required to compute the firmware hash H'_{FW} was measured. This operation is predominantly influenced by the computational capabilities of the device, and for the selected ECG device, the mean computation time was 0.471 sec.
- Benchmark 3:* This metric corresponds to the time required for the transmission of H'_{FW} and i from the ECG device to the PUF instance over the UART communication interface. To address potential synchronization issues, a 3 sec delay was introduced to provide the PUF-hosting platform with sufficient time for data processing, ensuring stable data transfer and preventing the ECG device from overwhelming the receiver with excessive data. The overall average time recorded for this process was 3.112 sec.
- Benchmark 4:* This step corresponds to the SD card read latency associated with retrieving the challenge C_i and helper data $Synd_i$. A 11.3kB challenge file required approximately 1597ms to open, read, and close whereas a smaller 1.2kB helper data file completed the same sequence in 513ms. Thus, the resulting mean time was 2.110 sec.
- Benchmark 5:* The time needed for generating the PUF-based final key K'_i by the proposed KDF was measured in this step, yielding to an average time of 0.035 sec.

Fig. 4. Overview of the Low-End CMD's evaluation process

- vi. **Benchmark 6:** Final key transmission to the ECG. Final key forwarding, which utilizing the proposed mechanism is essentially an attestation key, is a critical step in securely transmitting the derived key K'_i to its intended recipient. To mitigate race conditions and ensure data integrity, 1 sec delay has been incorporated into this process, preventing out-of-order execution issues that could otherwise result in incomplete or corrupted key transmission. The overall average time recorded for this process was 1.001 sec.
- vii. **Benchmark 7:** Nonce signing is essential for preserving message integrity before transmitting data the gateway for verification. By utilizing an HMAC-SHA-256 cryptographic function, the system generates a cryptographic signature that authenticates the nonce while ensuring that secret keys remain protected. The resulting mean time for the ECG device to sign the nonce was 0.001 sec.
- viii. **Benchmark 8:** The complete operation of the PUF encompasses the processes evaluated in Benchmark 4 and Benchmark 5, in addition to the UART communication required to transmit the derived key to ECG device. This benchmark highlights the interconnected nature of the PUF operations, which combine data extraction, cryptographic processing, and communication. While both SD card access and UART communication introduce latency, the overall performance of these steps is crucial for ensuring the efficiency and reliability of the PUF's secure functionality in resource-constrained IoT environments. An average time of 3.146 sec was measured for such an operation, highlights the efficiency of the proposed design.
- ix. **Benchmark 9:** This metric evaluates the harmonic interaction of the PUF instance with the ECG device. Its evaluation included all stages starting after the H'_{FW} and i acquisition to the secure transmission of the attestation key, considering also the measures to mitigate racing conditions due to UART interface, while underscores the intricate interplay necessary for achieving seamless PUF integration. Despite its complexity,

the synchronization delay proved essential for ensuring stable communication and preventing functional errors, thus safeguarding the integrity of the entire process. By integrating these elements within the ECG device, the evaluation demonstrated the feasibility of secure PUF-based operations in far-edge devices. It highlighted the critical importance of addressing latency, computational demands, and synchronization protocols to facilitate a reliable and efficient implementation.

- x. **Benchmark 10:** This benchmark encompassed the entire process of extracting trustworthiness evidence, incorporating operations such as Bluetooth communication, UART communication, and data extraction from the SD card.

The table below summarizes the experimental results obtained related to the aforementioned benchmarks.

TABLE I
END-TO-END AUTHENTICATION BENCHMARKING RESULTS

Benchmark	Min (sec)	Max (sec)	Mean (sec)
Benchmark 1	2.117	2.942	2.374
Benchmark 2	0.471	0.473	0.471
Benchmark 3	3.112	3.114	3.112
Benchmark 4	2.101	2.119	2.110
Benchmark 5	0.033	0.055	0.035
Benchmark 6	1.001	1.001	1.001
Benchmark 7	0.001	0.001	0.001
Benchmark 8	3.135	3.175	3.146
Benchmark 9	6.247	6.279	6.258
Benchmark 10	9.951	11.935	10.539

V. CONCLUSIONS

The benchmarking analysis provides valuable insights into the system's capability to execute intricate security processes on far-edge devices while maintaining impressive efficiency. Among the total execution time of 10.539 seconds for the trustworthiness evidence extraction, three key contributors dominate: SD card access (2.110s, 20%), Bluetooth communication (2.374s, 22.5%), and UART synchronization delays (4s, 38%). These factors constitute over 80.5% of the total runtime. Despite that, the generation and exchange of complete trust evidence remain feasible within a practical time frame,

affirming the viability of deploying SRAM PUF-based secure authentication protocols in constrained environments.

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